

pers and leafolders. Tests conducted by the AICRIP plant physiology section show Govind can sustain drought for 9 days during the vegetative stage. It is a low tillering variety and should use closer spacing (20 cm × 10 cm) with 2-3 seedlings/hill when transplanted. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Ratoon rice can yield well

R. L. Nayak, M. Das, and S. S. Mandal, Agronomy Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani 741235, Nadia, West Bengal, India

Nine medium-duration rice cultivars were tested for ratoon growth and yield in a randomized block design with three replications during 1980-81 dry season in West Bengal, India. Four of the cultivars were also grown as a main crop during 1980 wet season.

The dry season crop was harvested in summer and allowed to grow as a ratoon crop during 1981-82 wet season. Nitrogen at 20 kg/ha was topdressed during early vegetative phase and pesticide was sprayed prior to flowering. No irrigation was used because 1,000 mm rainfall fell during crop growth.

Some cultivars showed good ratooning ability and matured about 14 days earlier

Grain yield and days to maturity of rice grown as a main crop in wet and dry seasons and as a ratoon crop after the dry season crop. West Bengal, India, 1980-82.

Cultivar	Main crop				Ratoon crop	
	Grain yield (t/ha)		Days to maturity		Grain yield (t/ha)	Days to maturity
	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season	Dry season		
IET3273	3.4	3.9	115	130	1.8	101
IET3305		4.2		130	1.2	101
IET3306		3.4		130	0.5	101
IET3629	2.4	4.8	110	140	2.7	95
IET3630	3.1	3.9	114	130	1.5	101
IET4555		4.7		140	2.1	95
IET5857	3.3	3.1	118	130	0.4	101
Ratna		4.5		130	0.6	101
Local		3.8		130	0.7	101
CD (0.05)		0.46			0.27	

than the main wet season crop and a month earlier than the main dry season crop.

IET3629 yielded highest (2.7 t/ha) in the shortest time (95 days) (see table). Its ratoon yield was 12% higher than main crop yield in wet season and 44%

less than main crop yield in dry season. It matured 15 days (wet season) and 45 days (dry season) earlier than the main crops.

Other cultivars with good ratooning ability were IET4555 (2.1 t/ha) and IET3273 (1.8 t/ha). □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Sheath rot incidence in cultivars grown at different nitrogen levels

A. K. Misra and S. C. Mathur, Plant Pathology Division, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack 753 006, Orisso, India

Incidence of sheath rot caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* was recorded for 26 rice cultivars that received 50, 100, 150, and 200 kg N/ha at CRRRI farm during 1981 kharif. Only Pankaj showed resistance at all nitrogen levels. Six cultivars were moderately resistant, 8 were moderately susceptible, and 11 were susceptible (see table).

In general, sheath rot susceptibility

Reaction to sheath rot of 26 rice cultivars grown at different nitrogen levels, CRRRI, Cuttack, India, kharif 1981.

Cultivars	Disease score ^d at different nitrogen levels			
	50 kg/ha	100 kg/ha	150 kg/ha	200 kg/ha
Pankaj	0	0	0	0
	<i>Resistant</i>			
	<i>Moderately resistant</i>			
CR294-548-1, RTM68	0	1	3	3
Jagannath, IR28, IR36	1	3	3	3
IR8	0	3	3	3
	<i>Moderately susceptible</i>			
CR318-461	1	3	3	5
CR318-549, PR106	1	3	5	5
CR316-639-1, IR4432-664-2	1	5	5	5
IR2071-178-3, CR.316-639-2, IR4432-664-1	3	3	5	5
	<i>Susceptible</i>			
CR318-548-7	1	3	3	7

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